

Weed control economics in transplanted rice (TPR)

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We evaluated the economics of prevailing weed control practices for TPR at RRS, Moncompu, during the 1988-89 monsoons (Jun-Oct) and wet season (Nov-Mar).

Three herbicides were tested against manual weeding in randomized block design with three replications. MO-7 rice (115 d) was transplanted at 15- × 15-cm spacing with 90-20-38 kg NPK/ha in a silty clay wetland. Herbicides were applied 6 d after transplanting (DT). Weeds were manually removed when they appeared in a weed-free check (WFC), and at 20 and 40 DT in plots hand-weeded twice (HWT).

Weed infestation was heavy. Dominant weed species were *Echinochloa colona*, *E. crus-galli*, *Ischaemum rugosum*, *Cyperus iria*, *C. difformis*, *Fimbristylis miliacea*, *Limnophila indica*, *Monochoria vaginalis*, *Ludwigia perennis*, and *Marsilea quadrifolia*.

Results exhibited similar trends for the three seasons. Pooled analysis showed statistically insignificant interaction between season and treatment. All

herbicides were equally effective in weed control, were comparable to HWT, and superior to the unweeded check (see table).

Herbicide treatments resulted in grain yields on par with WFC, but significantly superior to HWT. Applying butachlor 50 EC at 1.0 kg ai/ha 6 DT was most economic for controlling weeds in TPR in Kerala. □

Economics of weed control treatments in transplanted rice, Kerala, India, 1988-89.^a

Treatment ^b	Dose ^c (kg ai/ha)	Weed dry weight (g/m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Gross return (\$/ha)	Benefit of weed control (\$/ha)	Cost of weed control (\$/ha)	Marginal benefit-cost ratio
Anilophos 30 EC	0.6	29.35	2.3	3.4	483	430	23	18.7
2,4-D EE 4 G	0.8	24.45	2.4	3.6	496	443	23	19.3
Butachlor 50 EC	1.0	32.10	2.3	3.5	474	421	15	28.1
Weed-free check (WFC)		4.63	2.4	3.9	496	443	98	4.5
Hand weeding twice (HWT)		33.78	2.0	3.2	412	359	69	5.2
Unweeded check		73.55	0.3	0.2	53	-	-	-
LSD (0.05)		18.91	0.7	1.4	-	-	-	-

^a Pooled mean of 3 seasons. ^b EC = emulsifiable concentrate. G = granule. ^c ai = active ingredient. Costs: anilophos = \$8.67/liter, 2,4-D EE = \$0.87/kg, butachlor = \$6.65/liter, rice gram = \$200/t, straw = \$5/t.

Integrated pest management—other pests

Golden snail (*Pomaces* sp.) use in animal feeds

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We studied nutrient composition of different golden snail meal forms and supplemental use in swine diets.

Meal forms were cooked and uncooked golden snail meal (GSM), golden snail meat meal, and golden snail shell meal. Feeds for growing/finishing pigs were pure commercial feed mash (CFM), CFM + 5% GSM, CFM + 10% GSM, and CFM + 15% GSM.

Twelve growing male pigs (F₂ - Large White/Landrace) were individually fed for 110 d. Response criteria were statistically analyzed using completely randomized design.

Cooked and uncooked GSM had similar nutrient values (Table 1). GSM

Table 1. Composition of different feedstuffs derived from golden snail on a dry matter basis.

	Golden snail meal meal (cooked)	Golden snail meal meal (uncooked)	Golden snail meat meal	Golden snail shell meal
Dry matter (%)	90.30	89.90	86.10	98.60
Gross energy (kcal/kg)	605.61	671.45	3336.27	
Crude protein (%)	14.62	17.15	62.48	4.30
Ether extract (%)	0.88	0.56	3.48	0.50
Crude fiber (%)	3.43	3.45	4.65	3.00
Nitrogen-free extract (%)	-	0.44	13.36	0.90
Calcium (%)	30.87	28.55	3.40	35.05
Phosphorus (%)	0.30	0.26	1.22	0.01

Table 2. Average production performance of growing finishing pigs fed a diet supplemented with different levels of GSM.^a

	CFM	CFM + 5% GSM	CFM + 10% GSM	CFM + 15% GSM
Initial wt (kg)	24.00	24.33	23.66	25.00
Final wt (kg)	85.50	88.16	83.50	91.67
Total wt gain (kg)	61.00	63.83	59.34	66.67
Daily wt gain (kg)	0.55	0.58	0.54	0.61
Total feed consumption (kg)	264.00	265.10	264.00	259.60
Daily feed consumption (kg)	2.40	2.41	2.40	2.36
Feed conversion efficiency	4.33	4.15	4.45	3.89

^a Statistical analysis showed insignificant differences among the treatments.

had satisfactory crude protein (14.62-17.15%), and minerals (ash), mainly Ca (28.55-30.87%).

Meat meal was more nutritionally balanced, with good gross energy and high crude protein. Ca and P were also

high with a 3:1 ratio. Golden snail meat meal can safely replace fish or meat meal in food animal diets.

Shell meal was Ca-rich, with 35.05% Ca. It could potentially replace oyster shell meal.

Table 2 shows average production performance of growing/finishing pigs fed GSM-supplemented diets. The response criteria—average daily gain, average daily feed consumption, and average feed conversion efficiency—

showed insignificant differences across treatments.

The results indicate GSM could be used as a feed supplement for growing/finishing pigs. □

Loss of rice grain yield and seedling vigor due to sheath rot (ShR) and mealy bug interaction

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We observed a severe ShR *Sarocladium oryzae* (Sawada) W. Gams and Hawksw. outbreak in Sep-Oct 1990 in IR20 ricefields infected with mealy bug *Brevinnia rehi* Lindinger.

The flag leaf of individual tillers was assessed and tagged with waterproof color tape according to ShR severity at grain maturity stage. The *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) was

used. About 100 samples, replicated five times, represented each severity class.

Mealy bugs inside ShR-infected sheaths were counted for each class. Panicles within seventy classes were bulked, dried separately. Thousand-grain weight and percent of healthy, discolored, and chaffy grains were recorded.

We evaluated seedling vigor after storage for 1 mo at room temperature with a standard test. Fifty seeds were incubated between double-layer blotter paper in 9-cm plates for 2 wk at 25°C with four replications per sample. We recorded the number of germinated seeds, and shoot and root lengths after 2 wk.

ShR severity was positively correlated ($r = 0.99^{**}$) with mealy bug population (see figure). Their interaction greatly reduced 1,000-grain weight, grain yield (9-77%), and healthy grains percentage; it increased chaffy and discolored grains.

Correlation of sheath rot severity and mealy bug population Sep-Oct 1990 at ACRI.

Seed germination and root length were significantly reduced, but shoot length was not. □

Water management

Water use by irrigated summer rice

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We measured use of water by summer rice through evapotranspiration and deep percolation. Soils were medium black, clay loam texture, pH 6.9, 0.82% organic C, infiltration rate 1.0-1.5 cm/h.

The technique used two 200-liter capacity leakproof drums, 60 cm in diameter and 90 cm high. One drum had

an open bottom; the second, a closed bottom. The drums were installed in oversized pits 60 cm deep and 65 cm in diameter in the ricefield, leaving about 30 cm of the drum height aboveground. The soil was backfilled layerwise and compacted to approximately the same bulk density as that of the surrounding soil.

Mean evapotranspiration use and deep percolation loss at different growth phases of summer rice.^a Maharashtra, India, 1987-89.

	Water use (mm)									
	Open-bottom drum					Closed-bottom drum				
	Transplanting to maximum tillering	Maximum tillering to flowering	Flowering to milk stage	Milk to maturity	Total (90 d)	Transplanting to maximum tillering	Maximum tillering to flowering	Flowering to milk stage	Milk to maturity	Total (90 d)
Total evapotranspiration + deep percolation	528.3	678.9	342.0	450.4	1999.6	280.8	372.9	203.9	271.0	1128.5
Average/d	21.1	22.6	22.8	22.5	-	11.2	12.4	13.6	13.6	-
Through evapotranspiration	-	-	-	-	-	280.8	372.9	203.9	271.0	1128.5
Through deep percolation	247.5	306.0	138.2	179.4	871.1	-	-	-	-	-
Deep percolation/d	9.9	10.2	9.2	8.9	-	-	-	-	-	-
Percolation (%)	46.9	45.1	40.4	39.8	-	-	-	-	-	-

^aAv for 3 yr.